

DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to the glory of God.

ABSTRACT

This project examines the non-achievement of laboratory as a factor for poor performance of students in Physics. With the aid of data collection, it is obvious that Physics cannot be in abstract. The sensitivity of laboratory practical to the knowledge of Physics cannot be overemphasized. This project suggests further research into challenges of Physics practicals.

The number of teachers that participated in the study were twenty. The teachers were selected from secondary schools across Obafemi-Owode Local Government in Ogun State.

The findings show that availability of laboratories facilitates teaching and learning of Physics as its non-availability brought set back to its teaching and learning.

It is thereby recommended that the teachers in various schools should improvise in aspect of Physics that are possible while school authorities should make provisions for the laboratory needs of the Physics teacher and students, and Government agencies should make proper supervision.

CHAPTER ONE

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Laboratory is a room, building or part of a building that is specially built for teaching by demonstration of theoretical phenomenon into practical terms. The laboratory experience enables students to translate what seems to be abstract into practical realities, thereby enhancing their understanding of the learning process. The study of Physics in secondary schools takes place in laboratories. This is to enable easy access and usage of material resources stocked in the laboratories for teaching and learning, not only during practical classes but also during normal classroom teaching. Physics adopts laboratory method of teaching. The laboratory method is an individual or group activity involving two-way approach namely: the exercise approach and the experimental approach. Okoli and Osuafor (2020) pointed out that this method offers students the opportunity to develop scientific skills and attitude such as objectivity, communication, questioning, formulating hypothesis, analyzing data, critical thinking, carefulness, open-mindedness, making inference and analyze data. Scientific skills can only be effectively developed if Biology laboratory resources are effectively utilized.

The school laboratories that are well designed, stocked and safe for teaching and learning of science ensure active practical exercises (Katcha, 2015).

Teaching of Physics cannot be effective without interaction between the teacher, students and the environmental resources. The Physics curriculum is planned to enable the teacher use activity oriented, child-centered approach (guided inquiry) to teach. Nzewi and Nwosu (2020) laboratory resources can therefore be said to be supplies of teachers, learners, laboratory assistants/technologists, instructional materials and other necessary devices made available to the school in order to increase the wealth of knowledge, which gives help, support in the teaching and the learning process in secondary schools.

Laboratory resources are categorized into two namely: human and material resources.

This study therefore seeks to investigate the impacts and availability and the extent to which the available laboratory resources are being utilized in Teaching and learning Physics in Obafemi/Owode Local Government Area, OgunState. It also intends to look into the loopholes that can be created where the laboratory resources are not available .

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Teaching and learning of sciences ought to be simplified, comprehensive and concrete. Extensive use of laboratory resources makes science interesting, stimulating and understandable to the learners. The success of science students in secondary schools largely depends on the availability and effective utilization of available human and material resources.

The dwindling students' performance in science subjects especially in Physics has been a source of concern to all stakeholders - the parents, teachers, students, Physics education researchers, government and the general public. Despite the efforts by Physics educators, the performance of many students in Physics is still at abysmal level. In essence there are still gaps in the efforts and results available. This situation is easily attributed to factors of laboratory equipment supplied, gender factors and attitudes of students to Physics teaching and learning among others. With laboratory equipment, the modern trend emphasizes laboratory practicals as an integral part of classroom instruction in teaching and learning Physics with preandpost laboratory discussion if students have to learn the subject effectively in theory and practical. hence , the need for this research work .

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study work is to find out the impacts of non availability of laboratory in secondary schools on students academic achievement in Physics , specifically the study intends ;

1. To identify the availability of equipment, apparatus, materials and chemicals in the Physics laboratories at the secondary school stage in Obafemi/Owode Local Government.
2. Find out the level in which secondary schools use laboratory in Obafemi/Owode local Government secondary schools.
3. To find out the impacts of the use of school laboratories on academic achievements of Physics students in Obafemi/Owode local Government secondary schools.
4. To find out the relationship between the availability and the use of science laboratories with the academic achievement of Physics students in Obafemi/Owode local Government secondary schools.

1.4 Research Questions

1. Do secondary schools have Physics laboratories?
2. Are Physics Laboratories well equipped?
3. Can Physics be taught in abstract?
4. How does laboratory resources impacts teaching and learning Physics ?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant usefulness of laboratory on student's achievement in Physics .

HO₂: There Is no significant usage of laboratory on students' achievement in Physics .

HO₃ There is no significant impact of laboratory usage on Physics students' achievement

HO₄ There is no significant differences between availability and non availability of laboratory on Physics students' achievement.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The information that shall be gathered in this research will be useful since the teaching and learning of Physics is essential for achieving success in any science and technology development of any nation, as there is a direct relationship between achievement in Physics on one hand and economic growth of any given country on the other hand. Findings from this study will also be of benefit in planning and budgeting, so as to provide enough fund to support science subjects like Physics in schools, building laboratories, train more Physics teachers, purchase adequate teaching and learning resources including books, teaching models, laboratory equipment, apparatus and chemicals. Furthermore, findings will hopefully influence further research on how the use of laboratory and promote learning of Physics for development of the nation.

The findings of this study will help the ministries of education and relevant stake holders including the teachers in evaluating students' performance in their various capacities. It will also give curriculum developers new insights into emerging issues on performance and influence the authorities on policy formation; because improved Physics performance will give them opportunities to pursue career in medical, environmental, agricultural sciences , engineering , technical , vocational and other related science programmes in institution of higher learning in the country. This will enable the country in the areas of power generation , poverty eradication , technological breakthrough among others .

1.7 Scope of the Study

This research is to investigate the impacts of availability or non availability and utilization of laboratory , human and material resource in some secondary schools. The study will determine the extent to which the availability of laboratory resources in Physics laboratories impact the students in secondary schools where they were being utilized at the same time

look into the lapses of its non availability in some quarters . The study will be limited to senior secondary schools Physics teachers in Obafemi Owode Local Government Area of Ogun State.

1.8 Limitation of the Study

Likely limitations to this research work may include: time constraints, financial constraints, lapses from respondents among others.

1.9 Operational Definition of Terms

Impact: to influence; to affect or cause (something) to happen; bring about an action or a change which is a result or consequence of an action or other cause.

Laboratory: a room or building equipped for scientific experiments, research, or teaching, or for the manufacture of drugs or chemicals.

Science: the intellectual and practical activity encompassing the systematic study of the structure and behaviour of the physical and natural world through observation and experiment.

Physics : A core science subject which studies motion , light , electricity and oscillating etc

Availability: the quality of being able to be used or obtained.

Achievement: a thing done successfully with effort, skills or courage

Practical: Relating to action and practice rather than ideas and thought.

Equipment: sets of tools or objects used to achieve a particular objective.

Apparatus: Technical equipmentdesigned for a particular use.

Materials: a thing something else is made out of.

Resources: Materials available in our environment which are technologically available.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

2.0

INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, related literature to the topic will be discussed under the following sub-headings:

Conceptual Framework

Theoretical Framework

Empirical Studies

Summary of Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Concept of Physics

Physics is a branch of science which deals with the study of matter and energy . The word ‘PHYSICS’ originates from the Greek word, ‘PHYSIS’ , which means nature and natural characteristics. Physics as a body of scientific knowledge, deals with the study of events in the universe, both remote and immediate universe. In actual sense, Physics deals with the behaviour of matter as well the interaction of matter and natural forces. Physics deals with matter ranging from sub-atomic level or particles to the stars, including the entire galaxy. Physics as an experimental science subjects utilises the scientific method to formulate and test hypotheses that are based on observation of the natural world. The goal of Physics is to use the result of the experiments formulate scientific laws, usually expressed in the language of Mathematics, which can then be used to predict other phenomena. Physics is a fundamental science subject because other natural sciences deal with system that obey law of Physics. According to Wikipedia(2023), Physics is the natural science of matter, involving the study of matter, its fundamental constituents, its motion and behaviour through space and time, and the related entities of energy and force. A scientist who specializes in the field of Physics is called a Physicist. The objectives of Physics are aimed at enabling the students who are adequately trained to acquire the following skills:

- Observing carefully and thoroughly.
- Drawing and labeling accurately observed materials.
- Reporting completely and accurately what is observed.
- Organizing information acquired by the above processes.
- Generalizing on the basis of the acquired information.

- Predicting as a result of these generalizations
- Designing experiments (including control where necessary).

Using models or other resource materials to explain phenomena where appropriate.

Continuing the process of enquiry where new data does not conform to prediction. (Onimisi 2016).

Based on the above objectives, a trained Physics student invariably is a scientist since all the scientific processes (state the problem; gather information; form hypothesis; perform experiments; analyze data; draw conclusions; form theories and laws) are hierarchically performed in the Physics laboratory. These cannot be achieved if the resources in the laboratories are not adequately utilized. Physics as an indispensable part of human activity is important to man and the society. The following are some of the usefulness of Physics to man.

- It provides an in-depth, scientific understanding of how all matter and energy interact with each other.
- Helps the individual to understand natural phenomenon
- Enables the individual to question superstition due to sustained interest from a comprehension of the causes of events.
- Promotes understanding of the relation of man to his environment.
- Prepares the individual for vocational selection such as medicine, dentistry, agriculture, engineering, teaching and so forth.
- Inculcates scientific attitudes and skills in solving problems.
- Improves the individual factual knowledge and stimulates scientific reflective thinking so as to produce a better informed individual.

Physics has also contributed immensely to the development of the society in the following ways: understanding of matter and energy relationship, understanding of space technology, development of technological gadgets, formulation of laws and theories.

2.1.2

Concept Of Laboratory

2.1.3

Concept of Laboratory Resources

Resources are source of supply, support, or aid, especially one that can readily drawn upon when needed. Resources as defined by Hornby (2016) are supplies of something that a country, an organization or a person has and can use, especially to increase wealth. Hornby further explained that resources are things that can be used to help achieve an aim, e.g. a book, equipment etc that provide information for teachers and students. In the context of this work, resources are discussed as it concerns Physics laboratory.

Laboratory resources are those human and material resources that are available for teaching and learning process.

Laboratory resources can be viewed as supplies of individuals and materials whose utility in one way or the other help in the actualization of educational objectives. All resources have unique qualities of utility, availability and consumption (wikipedia, 2021). Resources are vital for any teaching-learning process to proceed effectively. The desirability of adopting material resources for teaching Physics cannot be over emphasized in making the lesson concrete and practicable. They are necessary tools that facilitate learning. Chime (2020) is of the opinion that resource materials enable the teacher to teach more effectively or better still enable the children to learn more readily. Learning resources motivate students and serve as effective ways to explain and illustrate subject content. In a similar vein, Oladipo (2018) asserted that resource materials facilitate understanding of concrete materials, creative motivation and interests for the subject. These laboratory resource materials reinforce learners to retain information for a long period of time. Chukelu (2019) agrees that utilization of material resources for teaching-learning processes has the following positive effects on the learners:

- Holds students' interest.
- Retains information.
- Provides concrete and realistic experience.
- Stimulates imagination and self-activity.
- Helps to clarify abstract ideas.

Laboratory resources are broadly classified into two, namely: human and material resources. Researchers have identified different types of resources. For instance, resources could be identified as human resources; natural resources; material resources; community resources; capital resources and personnel resources. Chimezie, Ike and Iwu(2022) categorized

resources into message, people, materials, devices, techniques, settings and the learner. For the purpose of this research work, only human and material resources are discussed.

Human Laboratory Resources otherwise called resource persons are people who possess more authentic knowledge and needed information and skill, and are also willing and able to communicate to students the information, and have the right or authority to give the information out. They can be foreigners or indigene. They provide wonderful opportunities through creative activities for self expression. Wikipedia (2021) view human resources as a term used to describe the individuals who make up a work force of an organization. Human resources are the skills, energies, talents, abilities and knowledge that are used for the production of goods or the rendering of services (Wikipedia, 2021). Resource persons also called human resources are expertise individuals with specialties in different professions. These specialized experts have the needed skills which can be transferred to others. Human resources are selected based on professionalism and talent not because of age, gender or location. Laboratory human resources are both academic staff as well as the laboratory staff. Nwagbo (2015) highlighted some of qualities of a Physics teacher as a competent resource person as: being emotionally stable, have good disposition, show a democratic and cooperative attitude. She/he should also demonstrate empathy, patience, humor and fairness. These personality traits of the teacher add to his effectiveness in teaching and learning of biology. Nwafor (2018) listed the professional duties of biology laboratory resource persons as follows:

- Help to determine the objectives of the school system.
- Provide laboratory facilities for use in the Physics laboratories.
- Help to develop relevant curricular and learning materials (like posters, charts, videos, tapes, real objects and specimens).
- Assist in the development and evaluation of resources for school learning.
- Serve as speakers on career days.
- Organize meetings, workshops, conference and seminars for teachers and or students
- Providing advice on budgeting, financing, purchasing, policies and procedures to be employed in Physics laboratories.
- Monitoring and evaluation of staff, students and all available material resources.

Material laboratory resources could be divided into four namely: audio-visual materials, visual/non-projected materials; audio media and projected media. Chimezie et al(2022) classified material laboratory resources as instructional media, instructional materials and educational media. For the purpose of this research work, Physics laboratory resource materials are classified into four as summarized below:

- (a) Classification as appealed to the two main senses.
- (b) Classification as print and non-print media.
- (c) Classification into two-dimensional and three-dimensional materials.
- (d) Classification into projected and non-projected media.
- (a) Classification as appealed to the two main senses (hearing and sight).

For effective utilization of learning resources, all the body sense organs must be involved. All learning is the result of sensory experience whether kinesthetic (touch), gustatory (taste), Olfactory (smell), auditory (hearing) or optical (seeing). The classification as appealed to the senses of hearing and sight are as follows:

Audio (auditory or aural) aids are material laboratory resources which appeal only to the sense of hearing. Audio media refers to those compliments that appeal to the sense of hearing. They produce sound which makes sense to the hearer; they can be used for group and individualized instruction and more importantly, for “homebound students” under special education schools. The teacher should break the content in small bits (task analysis) from simple to complex and specify the instructional objectives bearing in mind the age, ability level, interest and background of the learner (learner analysis); as well as the characteristics of the audio- resource material (material analysis) such as visibility, replaceability, compatibility (with other materials such as filmstrips, slide, programmes instructions); which make the medium of instruction more potential for educative purposes especially in developing countries.

Visual (optical) aids are resource materials which appeal only to the sense of sight. Audio-visuals are resource materials which appeal to the senses of sight and hearing at the same time. Egbu (2020) warned that audio visual instructional materials must produce both sound and hearing before classified as audio-visual material.

2.1.4 Availability of Laboratory Facilities

The lack of laboratories in schools is a problem for all subjects and especially in subjects such as biology, physics and chemistry. It is necessary for schools to have laboratories for practice, cabinet for technology class, the practical part is very important because you cultivate critical thinking to learn new knowledge, skills and work competences according to Reshiti (2015).

The use of aids in teaching is of importance as they help to stimulate Learners interest and promote understanding. According to Akoano and Akpokiere (2016) the teaching and learning of science which is practical course requires practical laboratory activities because experiment is the hall mark of science education. Uyoata (2016) also opined that meaningful learning of science requires the use of multisensory approaches where appropriate

instructional resources are selected and used. This is necessary because in this kind of learning students make use of more than one sense modality in learning. Dangbin (2018) also reported that practical activities using sufficient facilities enable learners to acquire cognitive skills such as formulation of hypothesis, making assumptions, designing investigations, understanding variables, observing, recording data etc and associated with these activities are scientific attitudes like curiosity, perseverance etc which are necessary for engaging in faithful science investigation. Oludare Abiodun and Ajayi (2016) also reported that there are no enough classrooms and laboratories. Laboratories have poor facilities and equipment and that, supplies of chemicals and reagents for experiments are quite low. Also schools lack laboratory assistance resulting in the poor maintenance and obsolete nature of laboratory facilities. Adepoju (2020) also reported that the quality of the products of the education system is daily depreciating due to obsolete, inadequate or even non-availability of materials. There is a general consensus among science educators that science teaching in schools has continued to be theoretical and not practically oriented (Ihieglulem 2016, Oludare Abiodun and Emmanuel 2019) As a result of this learners do not think practically and they are not able to apply the knowledge acquired. Little encouragement is given to learners to find out things for themselves instead they are being fed with facts and dogmas. As a result of this many science classrooms are characterized by the purpose of passing examination. Supporting this view Ogu (2018) reported that in most schools emphasis is more on the memorization of facts with a view to passing examination and less on the method of finding out the facts and learning to apply them. Another related problem is the practice in which teachers are not involved in planning and procurement of relevant instructional facilities for use in schools. According to Uyoata (2016) truckloads of items some of which are so strange and not related to the contents of the science curriculum are imposed on the teachers. Such materials are packed away where they collect dust for years which leads to malfunctioning of such facilities. They may lie waste because the teacher does not know how to use. And when they are faulty the replacement parts are hardly available.

2.1.5 Utilization of Laboratory Resources

The process of managing and organizing resources for teaching and learning is referred to as resource utilization (Lewin 2000) Resources utilization has to do with the extent to when facilities are provided to schools, these are three possibilities, they are either used effectively or inefficiently or they may remain unused. When item of equipment is maximally used such as equipment is effectively utilized. If the equipment is not maximally used it can be said to be underutilized. When there is so much pressure on the use of an equipment this may result to over utilization which could lead to breakdown of such item of equipment.

Teaching learning facilities improves the quality of teaching and make learning content meaningful. According to Ihiegbulem (2006) resource materials utilization during practices lessons inculcates in the students the spirit of careful observation, manipulative skills, respective thinking and creativity in the learners, Lewin (2000) however reported that Biology facilities are only important when they are used. One of the major problems facing the teaching and learning of Physics is connected with the management of available resources (Ogunleye, 2003) movement of resources requires the Physics teacher himself to be resourceful and creative and be careful in handling and using available facilities are handled cautiously especially the fragile ones. This is necessary because once the facilities are misused they cannot offer the best service required.

2.1.6 Maintenance of Facilities

The process in which good care is taken of tools and equipment to prolong their life span is referred to as maintenance. It involves all activities put in place to keep and restore the condition of facilities. Momoh and Onjewu (2016) define maintenance as any action or group of action taken to keep a facility in good working condition for as long as possible. When activities such as repairs, servicing, greasing etc are put in place to keep or restore the component of an item, the item is being maintained.

Laboratory equipment and facilities must be adequately taken care of in order to ensure their normal working conditions. Maintenance prevents deterioration and also weeds out obsolete items which no longer serve the required function. Momoh and Onjewu (2016) identified the followings as objectives of maintenance of facilities:

- To ensure that facilities are always available to provide services to for maximum benefits to staff and students.
- To ensure operational readiness of facilities for continuous service so as to reduce losses which may result from down time?
- To protect operating personnel and save facilities
- To extend the use of the facility for maximum benefit. Maintenance could be routine ongoing activities such as daily or weekly cleaning of the laboratory equipment and facilities, it could be periodic activities such as inspection and lubrication of parts of equipment to ensure continued working condition or corrective maintenance which include activities carried out to fix back a failed equipment or facility maintenance also involves the security of the equipment and facilities. Security here covers protection from physical damage from pests, fire, rain etc. It also pertains to protection from theft or unauthorized use.

Teachers should not wait for an equipment to breakdown completely before it is serviced. Report of the need for repairs or replacement of equipment must be made to school authority with the view to making immediate arrangement for the repairs and maintenance to avoid waste and depreciation.

However it has been reported that one of the major problems facing the teaching and learning of science is connected with the management of available resources (Ogunleye, 2013) that inability to appropriately manage resource in the laboratory is a sign of poor management. Kalat (2016) also reported poor maintenance culture among teachers. That outright hostility, manhandling, inferior texture, weathering, over use etc are among the factors inhibiting proper management of facilities. Moses (2016) reported that maintenance culture is very poor in Nigerian schools, homes, offices and industries. That facilities and equipment are laying waste due to breakdown; some are forced to breakdown by dust and cobwebs due to negligence and lack of care.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Piaget's Cognitive Constructivist Learning Theory.

Piaget's cognitive constructivist theory was propounded in (1973) and proposed that children progress through a sequence of four stages, assumed to reflect qualitative differences in children's cognitive abilities. Limited by the logical structures in the different developmental stages, learners cannot be taught key cognitive tasks if they have not reached the particular stage of development. Piaget emphasized on the holistic approach to learning. To him a child constructs understanding through exploring and experiencing his or her environment. Later in (1985) Piaget expanded this theory to explain how new information is shaped to fit with the learner's existing knowledge, and existing knowledge is itself modified to accommodate the new information. The major concepts in this cognitive process include:

- **Assimilation:** it occurs when a learner perceives new objects or events in terms of existing schemes or operations. This information is compared with existing cognitive structures.
- **Accommodation:** it occurs when existing schemes or operations have been modified to account for a new experience.
- **Equilibration:** it is the master developmental process, encompassing both assimilation and accommodation. Anomalies of experience create a state of disequilibrium which can be only resolved when a more adaptive, more sophisticated mode of thought is adopted. Piagetian constructivist theory generally regards the purpose of education as educating the individual child in a fashion that supports the child's interests and needs; consequently, the

child is the subject of study, and individual cognitive development is the emphasis. This is a child-centered approach that seeks to identify, through scientific study, and the natural part of cognitive development. It also assumes that learners come to classrooms with ideas, beliefs, and opinions that need to be altered or modified by a teacher who facilitates this alteration by devising tasks and questions that create dilemmas for the learners. Considering the educational reflections of this theory, Piaget sees the child as continually interacting with the world around the child, solving problems that are presented by the environment and learning occurs through taking action to solve these problems. The laboratory work in this study will also be based on these principles. Within Piaget's theory, the basis of learning is discovery: to understand is to discover, or reconstruct by rediscovery and such conditions must be complied with if in the future individuals are to be developed who are capable of production and creativity and not simply repetitive. According to Piaget, children go through stages in which they accept ideas they may later discard as wrong. Understanding, therefore, is built up step by step through active participation and involvement. Piaget further states that children begin to think logically between the age of 8 and 11 years, a stage he called the concrete operational stage of development. The average age for senior secondary schools year one (SSI) students (the targeted population for the study) is 11 years and above which implies that learners at this age can apply logical thought to practical works and be able to understand them better.

Laboratory activities require meaningful learning, i.e. learning that involves critical and creative thinking. Piaget's ideology supports this with the idea of logical thinking. This implies that teachers should create situations that would help the learners to discover facts by themselves. In this case, the teacher should establish an explorative environment for the learners to explore facts or truth by themselves. Prepackaged information can lead only to rote memorization of facts. Rote memorization is of no substantial benefit to the learner because it is not of much benefit in the exploration of the environment and the solution of problem. Individual acquires information through his interaction with the materials and the environment. Such information is retained and utilized for the solution of the environmental problem. Piaget's cognitive constructivist learning theory is related to the present study the availability and utilization of laboratory resources in teaching and learning biology in secondary schools; because laboratory work encourages students' active participation, critical thinking, problem solving abilities and others. Hence these proposition/assumptions will be embedded in the instructional strategy.

2.3 Empirical Review

There are several related studies to the survey on the impact and availability of laboratory resources in teaching and learning Physics. Ona (2017) in a study examined the effects of integrating theory with practicals on students' achievement in Physics. Four research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. A quasi experimental design was adopted for the investigation. A sample of five schools was used for the study. From the result of the study, it was observed that students perform poorly in Physics examinations because of the theoretical method of teaching that dominate most classrooms. As a result of this, students lack necessary skills which are the ultimate goal of any scientific and technological development. The study also revealed that those students' who were taught Physics through integrating theory with practical which utilizes Physics resources improved tremendously in their performance and acquisition of Physics skills. It was therefore recommended that theoretical aspect of teaching Physics should not be separated from practical activities. Additionally, efforts should be made by the government to provide necessary materials and equipment needed for meaningful and functional scientific knowledge in our schools. This result shows that performance of students in Physics had been poor over the years. Chukelu (2009) in a review of the effects of Physics practical activities on students' process skills acquisition in Abuja municipal Area council revealed that practical activity method of teaching Physics which utilizes resource materials was more effective in fostering students' acquisition of theoretical learning in Physics. A survey research conducted by Okoli (2016) on the effects of laboratory approach on academic achievement of Physics students of different levels of scientific literacy revealed that in Physics particular, the trend has shown that they have consistently been achieving low. Okoli attributed low performance of students in Physics to careless reading, wrong use of time, and inappropriate use of material resources while on the part of the teachers, incompetence and laziness, wrong experimental set-up and misinterpretation of results. The survey recommended that laboratory resources which are always complained by students and teachers to be lacking should be provided.

Additionally, adequate laboratory resources should be made available to schools and teachers should utilize resource materials when teaching by adopting laboratory teaching methods. A survey research on the equality in the distribution of educational resources in Ogun state secondary schools conducted by Obafemi (2017), he argued that since resources are inadequately distributed in schools, there is every tendency that poor performance recorded in results is its output. His findings further revealed that the methods adopted by the State and Federal Ministry of Education in the provision, distribution and management of human and

material resources affected not only the teachers' teaching methods but also the performance of the students whom they teach.

The results also indicated that 7.9% of Nigerian schools have no teaching and learning resources, equipment for science, home economics, arts and sports were lacking in majority of the schools. The product of the deficiencies is poor performance of students in various levels of examinations. He recommended that the government should distribute financial, human and material resources equally to all schools irrespective of location or level. He also recommended monitoring of the distributed resources for effective utilization of such resources.

2.4 Appraisal of Literature

The review of literature was presented under conceptual framework, theoretical framework, review of empirical studies and summary literature review. In the conceptual framework, it was noted that Physics as a branch of science required the use of laboratory resources to teach students effectively if maximum educational objectives are to be achieved. The use of laboratory resources for teaching Physics is very beneficial to the learners, teachers as well as the entire society hence its implementation is highly advocated in the teaching learning process. Utilization of laboratory resources involves seven basic functions: planning, co-ordinating, directing, organizing, supervising, monitoring and evaluation. Factors militating against effective utilization of laboratory resources include lack/insufficient fund, training, over enrolment of students into secondary schools, lack/inadequate materials for use in the laboratories, ignorance of teachers and students on effective use of resources, indiscipline among teachers and students, lack of qualified personnel to handle Physics practical classes effectively, inappropriate documentation of resources, lack of integrity, political constraints as well as logistics problems. The above problems could be effectively curbed through proper utilization of resources in Physics laboratories and maintenance of facilities.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

A descriptive design of survey type was adopted for this study with a view of getting adequate information

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study is the entire Physics teachers in Obafemi/Owode Local Governemnt Area, Ogun State.

3.3 Sample and Sampling procedure

Twenty Physics teachers were selected from various schools in Obafemi/Owode Local Government 'ten schools were purposely selected for the study'

3.4 INSTRUMENTS FOR DATA COLLECTION

The major instrument used for this research is questionnaire tagged 'Physics Laboratory Resources Questionnaire' (PLRQ)

3.5 Validation of the Instrument

The content and the face validity of instrument were considered by the project supervisor and other lecturers in the field of Physics and education.

3.6 Procedure For data collection

The researcher personally visited the schools selected; administer the questionnaires to the Physics teachers with the assistance of the management of the respected schools.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

Frequency, count and simple percentage were used to analyze the data

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter deals with interpretation of data and its analysis on the impacts of Use and Availability of laboratory Resources on Students' Achievements in Physics.

4.1 Analysis

The information collected in this heading were divided into four (4) different tables and preceded by the research questions. In this research work, twenty (20) questionnaires were distributed to Physics teachers in ten secondary schools. The frequency count of returned instruments and simple percentage were used for its analysis.

4.2 THE RESULTS OF QUESTIONNAIRES ADMINISTERED

RESEARCH QUESTION 1

'DO SECONDARY SCHOOLS HAVE PHYSICS LABORATORIES?'

To test the above research question, frequency responses obtained on each item was used to complete the percentage has shown below;

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	TOTAL
1		15	75	5	25	0	0	0	0	20
2		18	90	2	10	0	0	0	0	20
3		10	50	10	50	0	0	0	0	20
4		8	40	12	60	0	0	0	0	20
5		20	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	20
TOTAL		71	71	29	29	0	0	0	0	100

FINDINGS: These findings show that 71% of the entire respondents strongly agreed that secondary schools mostly have laboratory, while 29% agreed. This is an indication that most secondary schools have laboratories.

RESEARCH QUESTION 2

‘ARE PHYSICS LABORATORIES WELL EQUIPPED?’

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	TOTAL
6		5	25	15	75	0	0	0	0	20
7		0	0	0	0	15	75	5	25	20
8		12	60	8	40	0	0	0	0	20
9		0	0	0	0	8	40	12	60	20
10		20	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	20
Total		37	37	23	23	23	23	17	17	100

FINDINGS: The findings show that 37% strongly agreed, 23% agreed, 23% disagreed and 17% strongly disagreed that laboratories in schools especially Physics Laboratories are well equipped.

RESEARCH QUESTION 3

‘CAN Physics BE THOUGH IN ABSTRACT?’

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	TOTAL
11		5	25	5	25	5	25	5	25	20
12		5	25	5	25	5	25	5	25	20
13		12	60	8	40	0	0	0	0	20
14		10	50	10	50	0	0	0	0	20
15		20	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	20
TOTAL		52	52	28	28	10	10	10	10	100

FINDINGS: The findings shows that 52% respondents strongly agreed, 28% agreed, 10% disagreed and 10% strongly disagreed that Physics cannot be thought abstract.

RESEARCH QUESTION 4

HOW DOES LABORATORY RESOURCES IMPACTS TEACHING AND LEARNING OF Physics?

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	TOTAL
16		10	50	10	50	0	0	0	0	20
17		15	75	5	25	0	0	0	0	20
18		5	25	15	75	0	0	0	0	20
19		6	30	14	70	0	0	0	0	20
20		20	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	20
TOTAL		56	56	44	44	0	0	0	0	100

FINDINGS: The findings shows that 56% respondents strongly agreed, 44% agreed, 0% disagreed and strongly disagreed that Laboratory resources impacts teaching and learning of Physics.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDING

The role of laboratory is very crucial in the teaching and learning of Physics. 72% of Physics teachers in the target population are in support of the availability and equipment of the laboratory resources in their respective schools.

The first item of the questionnaire is 'most schools have laboratory' it was agreed upon by 100 while 0% disagreed to it.

The second item of the questionnaire is 'some schools have Physics Laboratory' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The third item of the questionnaire is 'some schools combined laboratory' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The fourth item of the questionnaire is 'Physics practicals were carried out in science Laboratory' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The fifth item of the questionnaire is 'Laboratory is available in my school' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The sixth item of the questionnaire is 'Our school Physics Laboratory is well equipped' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The sixth item of the questionnaire is 'Our school Physics Laboratory is well equipped' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The seventh item of the questionnaire is 'Our school Physics Laboratory is not well equipped' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The eighth item of the questionnaire is 'We have adequate resources' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The ninth item of the questionnaire is 'We do not have adequate resources' it was agreed upon by 0% respondents.

The tenth item of the questionnaire is 'We carryout practicals' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The eleventh item of the questionnaire is 'Physics can be taught is abstract' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The twelfth item of the questionnaire is 'Physics cannot be taught is abstract' it was agreed upon by 50% of the entire respondents while 50% disagreed to it.

The thirteenth item of the questionnaire is 'Physics is practical' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The fourteenth item of the questionnaire is 'Physics require instructional material' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents. This is in line with Junaid (2019) that 'it is a crime to teach without instructional material'

The fifteenth item of the questionnaire is 'Physics is a science' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The sixteenth item of the questionnaire is 'Practical enhances learning' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents. This is in line with Adewoyin (2019) 'instructional resources make learning meaningful.

The seventeenth item of the questionnaire is 'Learning resources make learning easier' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents. This is in consonance with Elegbede (2015) 'Instructional resources lessen teachers burden.

The eighteenth item of the questionnaire is 'Laboratory resources aroused learners interest' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The nineteenth item of the questionnaire is 'Laboratory resources lessen teachers burden' it was agreed upon by 100% respondents.

The twentieth and the last but not the least item of the questionnaire is 'laboratory resources

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary

This research work focuses on the impacts of use and availability of laboratory resources on students' achievement in Physics. The first chapter deals with the background to the study which serves as the introduction to the whole work.

Other information like purpose, research questions and limitation including scope of the study were not left out.

The second chapter looks into the review of related literature where some literature that are related to the study were contacted. The third chapter focuses on the methodology which involves the population of the study, sample and sampling technique, validation of instrument among others. The fourth chapter focuses on the data analysis and results of findings including the discussion of findings while the last chapter deals with the summary, conclusion and recommendation.

5.2 Conclusion

From the results of the findings, it can be concluded that the Impacts of laboratory in the teaching and learning Physics is very germane without laboratory, no meaningful teaching and learning of Physics can take place. This is because most topics in Physics have to do with practicals which must be handled as real objects. Practical aspects of Physics cannot be taught in abstract and the best place through which real deal can be carried out is the laboratory.

5.3 Recommendation

In line with the findings, the following recommendations are hereby made in respect to:

Students: Students should take their learning serious by cooperating with the teachers and participate in all theories and practicals in Physics.

Teachers: Teachers should do the needful by making necessary effort to put the students through the necessary aspects of Physics.

Schools: Management of schools should improvise for necessary resources that may not readily be available for teaching and learning to take p lace effectively.

Government: Government should continue to provide necessary amenities in schools to facilitate meaningful teaching and learning.

Parents: Parents should contribute their own quota in building the future of the students who are the hopes of tomorrow.

5.4 Suggestion for further studies

This research work has been carried out on the impacts of laboratory resources on the teaching and learning of Physics. Further research can be carried out on challenges facing practical classes in Physics.

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Appendix

NATIONAL TEACHERS' INSTITUTE, KADUNA

IBAF0 PGDE STUDY CENTRE

PHYSICS LABORATORY RESOURCES QUESTIONNAIRES

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	%	A	%	D	%	DS	%	TOTAL
1	Most schools have laboratory									
2	Some schools have Physics Laboratory									
3	Some schools combine laboratory									
4	Physics practicals were carried out in science laboratories									
5	Laboratory is available in my school									
6	Our school Physics laboratory is well equipped									
7	Our school Physics laboratory is not well equipped									
8	We have adequate resources									
9	We do not have adequate resources									
10	We carry out practicals									
11	Physics can be taught in abstract									
12	Physics cannot be taught in abstract									

13	Physics is practical								
14	Physics requires realia								
15	Physics is a science								
16	Practicals enhances learning								
17	Learning resources make learning easier								
18	Laboratory resources aroused learner's interest								
19	Laboratory resources lessen teachers' burden								
20	Laboratory resources assist learners								